

Qualis A3 ISSN: 2178-2008

ARTIGO

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Revista Processus de Estudos de Gestão, Jurídicos e Financeiros

Tariffs turbulences in 2025. Intellectual property trade barriers local trade protections vs tariffs

Turbulências tarifárias em 2025. Uma discussão sobre barreiras comerciais de propriedade intelectual, proteções comerciais locais e tarifas

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16846683

Recebido: 14/04/2025 | Aceito: 20/07/2025 | Publicado on-line: 13/08/2025

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Abstract

The paper focuses on economic theory intellectual property of marks, collective marks, and geographical indications of trade barriers towards tariffs. We analyze the increasing conflict and turbulence due to the trade rivalry between the U.S., Europe, and China revamped at the beginning of 2025. One strategy suggests indirect barriers, for example, Geographical Indication (GI) as the protection for local trade and against tariffs. The self-sufficient agriculture strategy or national security concern supports the protection of agricultural goods as Geographical Indications. The paper uses an example of Brazil's case using the 2019 Mercosul - Europe agreement, and recent meetings (2024) suggesting the trade flow from Europe to the U.S. Another expansion of European and Brazilian GI exports could be increasing Europe - Mercosur trade. Thus the result of the research is favorable to GI (using the European terroir interpretation) against the use of marks and collective marks as a countermeasure of tariff increase.

Key-words: Tariffs, Mark, Collective Mark, Geographical Indication, Local protection.

Resumo

O artigo se concentra na teoria econômica de propriedade intelectual de marcas, marcas coletivas e indicações geográficas, barreiras comerciais em relação a tarifas. Analisamos o crescente conflito e turbulência devido à rivalidade comercial entre EUA, Europa e China, reformulada no início de 2025. Uma estratégia sugere o uso de barreiras indiretas ou Indicação Geográfica (IG) como a principal proteção para o comércio local e contra tarifas. A estratégia de agricultura autossuficiente ou preocupação com a segurança nacional adiciona uma motivação à proteção de produtos agrícolas como Indicações Geográficas. O artigo usa como exemplo o caso do Brasil usando o acordo Mercosul - Europa de 2019 e reuniões recentes (2024)

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sugerindo aumentar o fluxo de comércio da Europa para os EUA. Outra expansão da exportação de IG europeia e brasileira pode estar aumentando o comércio Europa - Mercosul. Assim, o resultado da pesquisa é favorável à IG (usando a interpretação do terroir europeu) contra o uso de marcas e marcas coletivas como contramedida ao aumento de tarifas.

Palavras-chave: Tarifas, Marca, Marca Coletiva, Indicação Geográfica, Proteção Local.

1. Introduction

In the 1960s and 1970s, Europe Union (EU) progressively reduced its Most Favored Nation (MFN) tariffs under the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT). As multilateral liberalization lost momentum, the EU increasingly relied on bilateral and regional agreements to pursue trade objectives. The growth in Free Trade Agreements (FTAs), the Generalised Scheme of Preferences (GSP), and autonomous tariff suspensions reflects this trend. While these instruments enable flexibility, they also introduce complexity and erode the uniform application of the Most Favored Nation (MFN) principle. Recent events, 2025 tariff war, changed again international trade.

Has the recent U.S. tariff events² ended the economic globalization and general tariffs agreement negotiations? That theme must be discussed fairly because politics and society's environment do it emotionally and ideologically. Thus, the paper justifies itself as a theoretical and systematic analysis adding considerations about tariff and intellectual property, or marks (M), collective marks (CM), and geographical indications (GI), turbulence, strategies, and tariff countermeasures. They are protections called trade barriers by neoclassical economic theory (USTR 2025).

The paper aims to focus on intellectual property relations towards tariffs. By analyzing the legal foundations, historical evolution, and practical implementation of tariff instruments, we explore a complex and often contradictory strategy. The paper clarifies how much a market differentiation strategy based on M, CM, and GI is consistent with tariffs. As an example, we focus on Brazil's legislation and trade considering bilateral agreements. Thus, this part of the research is a case study of applied economics and public administration policies.

The discussion starts with tariffs and the recent struggle on tariffs exploring the complexity of possible strategies and the difference between tariffs and trade barriers. Brazil's case example introduces an alternative approach of a unilateral increase of tariffs in the agricultural sector. An articulated strategy with barriers and increased trade with new partners is a possible alternative. Alternatives are preferable to respond to tariffs against tariffs.

2. Methodology

The paper's has three methodological steps:

1) The first is a bibliographic research discussion about the definition and economic theory of tariffs to clarify the contexts and object of the paper. That section also clarifies what M, CM, and GI are different from tariffs, how those protections work and could be used in tariff global wars. A third part of that section shows the actual struggle, starting in April 2025, as a pivot mark for the future.

² <https://ustr.gov/about/policy-offices/press-office/press-releases/2025/march/ustr-releases-2025-national-trade-estimate-report>

2) A Second is a short study case of applied economy. That section analyzes Brazil's situation shows the possible impact on trade by tariff increases, and compares interpretations of strategies of marks, and geographical indications. We shows different positions and strategies for tariff increases in agricultural goods and claims Europe Mercosul's agreement fast development. That section was developed because of the author's experience in that field and research in Brazil. The aim is to show alternative strategies between barriers and tariffs.

3) The final section is a result discussion. How Geographical Indication and the relationships with other protection marks are impacted by tariffs? One orientation will suggest a strategy to strengthen GI signs as a barrier for local trade protection and self-sufficiency national security..

3. Discussion

People get hurt by new import tariffs because they seem attacked when, in reality, tariffs respond to the fault of decades of negotiations in international trade and government trade strategies. The reaction is to respond to the attacker with another attack or to think the attacker will lose the war because the tariffs will strike back, and the attacker will be affected too. These considerations are left to economy amateurs, journalists, or faking news influencers, a more complex story must be told.

A more rational explication must be built to clarify the problem with a knowledge of International trade. It doesn't mean to qualify tariffs as good or bad, but every tariff strategy or change depends on the local economic system, the import, and export balance in goods, services, and capital, the actual situation of global tariffs, and the likely impacts expected in the change of the present configuration. There are no emotions but quantitative and logical models to explore.

Moreover, a world without tariffs or world economic free trade is a utopia. If some countries have a competitive advantage, or build it based on production manufactured or services it seems no tariffs will be successful in the long term to protect national interests. Which country could produce the best product depends on the trade networks, supply chain, labor cost, and the demand for the good. The evolution of global trade had the supply chain reformulated many years ago when the U.S. and Europe dislocated production outside the blocks to reduce costs under the economic globalization idea (Jagdish Bhagwati 2004, Kei-Mu Yi, 1999, STIGLITZ 2006).

We also have to discuss the matter considering the product life cycle and the difference between activity sectors. In the last decades innovation expanded service sector activity and that expanded also information economy sector. Thus, not all the products, in the different sectors of activities, are affected in the same way by tariffs. What changes are expected and realized when the international trade system will change for more innovations and new products preferences? Are continuous fast changes a common future practice?

3.1 Tariffs

Tariffs are taxes or duties on imported or exported goods (Salvatore 2016, WTO 2023). Their function is to regulate trade, protect domestic industries, generate revenue, and sometimes as a political tool in trade wars. There are various types of tariffs depending on the import and export policy depending on the economy of each country. First Ad Valorem Tariffs are a percentage of the value of the imported good³.

³ https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/tariffs_e/tariff_data_e.htm

These can be divided into: Specific Tariffs (a fixed amount charged per unit of the imported good), or mixed/compound Tariffs (a combination of ad valorem and specific tariffs) (Stephen D. Cohen, Robert A. Blecker, and Peter D. Whitney, 2003, Ralph Gomory and William Baumol 2000).

Tariffs play a significant role in both national and international trade (Salvatore 2016). There are tariffs as V.A.T.⁴. VAT is an indirect internal tax people must pay within the country added to import tariffs. In almost all countries a foreigner has ways to claim V.A.T. detaxation when buying in another country. Tariffs' impact varies based on economic policies, trade agreements, and geopolitical strategies. Countries impose import tariffs to protect domestic manufacturers from external competition and boost local production. Export tariffs are used in industries like raw materials like rare earth minerals to gain from increasing external demand of production factors, like China is doing on rare minerals, OPEC selling petrol, Brazil limiting banking, petrol extraction or flights companies ports, etc.

Seeking the burden of tariffs at a global level, the world average tariff rates are generally low, averaging between 2% and 5% for most developed nations (WTO 2023). That is due to free trade agreements (FTAs) defined in the second half of the XX century. The World Trade Organization (WTO) was created to regulate and negotiate tariffs to ensure fair trade. Free Trade Agreements (FTAs) like NAFTA (now USMCA), EU Single Market, and RCEP have significantly reduced tariffs between member nations increasing globalization.

After 1995 was established the World Trade Organization (WTO) Replacing GATT, became the global trade body with enforcement mechanisms. In that decade were developed major free trade agreements: NAFTA (1994), EU expansion, and China's opening up to global trade, and 2001 China Joined WTO and marked its integration into global markets (Aaditya Mattoo and Arvind Subramanian.2008, WTO 2023). However, from 2000 there was the growth of bilateral & regional agreements (ASEAN, Mercosur, African Free Trade Zones). Tariffs vary significantly across global trade blocs, reflecting each region's trade policies and economic strategies⁵.

International economic theory explains the Economic functionality of tariffs (Johnson 1964, Edwards, van Wijnbergen 1987, Salvatore 2016). That is a body of economic theories that explain how countries interact economically. It covers topics such as world trade, investment, and exchange rates. A very short list of academics in that area was: Ricardian theory (Ricardo 1821) which explains how countries gain from trade and how those gains are distributed. Country similarity theory: Proposes that consumers in similar countries have similar preferences. Heckscher-Ohlin's theory explains how countries' endowments of land, labor, and capital determine their international trade patterns.

Porter's national competitive advantage theory explains how countries gain a competitive advantage. And finally, Paul Krugman's theory of world trade, known as the New Trade Theory (NTT), explains why countries trade similar products. His theory also explains why countries produce goods that they don't have a comparative advantage in producing (Blaug 1997).

However, according to Mark Blaug (1997) were not performing well as a science because of the principles and procedures used by economists. He thought that the theories economists produced were often irrelevant or unfalsifiable. M. Blaug believed that methodology could help economics become a better science. Paying attention to

⁴ https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/taxation/vat_en

⁵ <https://ttd.wto.org/en/resources/data-availability/tariffs-and-import-notifications>

questions of methodology can illuminate economic controversies. The fact is that all models are very complex and based on past trends.

It is possible to make predictions but as was in April 2025 the change was not predicted, not because it was unpredictable, but because not all alternatives are explored every day, so the economists and the central agencies reduce a range of studies and predictions using the most probable strategies someone decides they are to trust.

Tariffs imposed on imported goods are often criticized for raising prices (inflation) and disrupting trade, but they can also serve important economic, strategic, and political purposes as was previously said about developing countries (Cato 2017, Roeger, Welfens 2022). First, they protect domestic industries helping shield local businesses and manufacturers from foreign competition, giving them time to develop and remain competitive. Without tariffs, cheaper imports could flood the market, causing job losses and the decline of national industries.

That is the impact on developed when industrial production is transferred abroad, as it is for Europe and the U.S. because the developed country will be vulnerable to the goods not being produced inside anymore.

A secondary function of tariffs function is reducing trade deficits (Cato 2017, Roeger, Welfens, 2022, Méndez and Méndez 2007 Balistreri, Hillberry, and Rutherford 2011). A country with a large trade deficit (importing more than it exports) may use tariffs to discourage imports and encourage domestic production. The U.S. has a trade deficit with China and BRICS, so tariffs on Chinese goods are meant to reduce dependence on imports and politically with that block, which launched communication threats recently.

Third some industries, like defense, semiconductors, and energy, are considered critical for national security which means National Security and Supply Chain Protection. Import tariffs prevent excessive reliance on foreign suppliers, ensuring that essential goods can be produced domestically in times of crisis⁶.

Fourth, tariffs prevent unfair trade practices (Brander and Spencer 1983). Some countries like China and Europe subsidize their industries, artificially lowering the prices of their exports and making it impossible for other countries to compete fairly. Tariffs help level the playing field by increasing the value of these artificially cheap imports.

Fifth tariffs are generating government revenue (Salvatore 2016). Before income taxes, tariffs were one of the great sources of government revenue. Many developing nations still rely on tariffs as a funding source for infrastructure, healthcare, and education. Some African nations use tariffs on imported goods to fund public projects. While generating revenue tariffs also encourage domestic job growth with companies moving production back home, creating more jobs for local workers.

From above we conclude that tariffs are not realistic when are too critical to industries fully exposed to global competition like the following industries: defense, energy, semiconductors, or natural monopoly inside countries (water, electricity network or rail transports, public services, etc.). Governments cannot risk relying on foreign suppliers for essential goods. Tariffs are included in policy but depend on national strategies.

It must be considered, that some countries subsidize their industries (e.g., China in steel and solar panels), making it impossible for other nations to compete fairly⁷.

⁶ https://www.accountancyeurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/171130-Publication-Definition-of-Public-Interest-Entities-in-Europe_1.pdf

⁷ https://www.wto.org/english/res_e/booksp_e/anrep_e/wtr06-2b_e.pdf

Without tariffs, unfair trade practices like dumping (selling goods below cost) would destroy domestic industries. Without protections, some domestic industries would collapse, leading to mass job losses. Again many developing countries rely on tariffs as a source of government income. Without tariffs, these nations seek alternative ways to fund public services. In general, countries use tariffs as a bargaining tool in trade negotiations. Thus U.S. attitude depends on other countries' attitudes. A world without tariffs would eliminate a government's form of leverage for economic and political power.

The adjustment in the medium and long term will favor industries that benefit from Protectionism (Balistreri, Hillberry, and Rutherford, 2011, Méndez and Méndez 2007). Those industries are: national security, economic stability, or global competition like U.S. steel tariffs protecting domestic mills from Chinese dumping. Here there is a risk of higher costs for industries using steel (e.g., car manufacturers). Subsidies and tariffs shield farmers from foreign competition and price volatility from cheap global food imports, like the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) protects European ones. Here there is a risk of artificially high food prices for consumers but there is a strategic self-sufficiency and food sovereignty theory in favor.

The energy industries are problematic because of different sources and their geographical distribution. On the other side, some industries like technology (Electronics, Software, AI), need free trade and no tariffs, even with dependence on foreign suppliers for critical tech components (e.g., semiconductors). The supply chain of apparel and footwear brands uses global supply chains to minimize costs. It stimulates foreign labor and supply chain disruptions. It must be added the problem of port and airport townships and contract space rent, the logistics hubs, and corporations' ownership.

There are financial considerations to discuss too. The macroeconomic theory explains the GDP with formulas and models in which all variables (consumption, investments, import, export, governmental expenses, etc.) are linked to the monetary and real economy (Mankiw, 1998). The adjustment in policies and decisions immediately affects all variables making the GDP expand or reduce with impacts on labor and capital markets. It must also be said that some industries thrive under protectionist policies (tariffs, subsidies, import restrictions), while others benefit from free trade (low or no tariffs, global market access).

As an option, a nation chooses to devalue its currency in response to another nation's increase in import tariffs. Here several risks and consequences can arise. First, it will raise inflationary pressure. Devaluation often leads to higher import costs. That can contribute to inflationary pressures within the country. Imported goods become more expensive, affecting consumers and potentially have higher prices (Mankiw 1998).

In summary, protectionism (or increasing tariffs) serves for: 1) National security industries (defense, energy), 2) Job protection in vulnerable sectors (manufacturing, agriculture), 3) Preventing unfair trade practices (dumping, subsidies), and free trade is better for: 1) Industries that rely on global supply chains (tech, fashion), 2) Consumers who benefit from lower prices. 3) Businesses that rely on export markets.

3.2. Trade Barriers: Marks, Collective Marks and Geographical Indications

By focusing on Marks (M), Collective Marks (CM), and Geographical Indications (GI), these indirect protections are intellectual property protections not direct trade barriers and no tariff. Their aim is to help differentiate products based on quality, origin, or branding not to increase government revenue directly barriers. They are generally

used at the end of the supply chain near the customer or B2C to differentiate products and services, thus, the rest of the supply chain is a B2B affair.

From the point of view of the customers a barrier and a tax increase the final price. Thus, the differentiation between barriers and tariffs is: that a tariff is a tax imposed by a government on imported goods and services. The barriers do not impose costs on imports but create brand value and exclusivity, a higher price of a product or service relative to a basic possible reduction with the latest technology available, and an indirect barrier to competition.

Table 1 - Key Differences between Tariffs and protections

Feature	Tariff	Protection like Marks
Type of Barrier	Tax on imports	Legal protection of brand/identity
Effect on Prices	Increases import prices	Creates brand exclusivity but does not impose direct costs
Government Revenue	Yes, from tariff collection	No direct revenue, but can support domestic industries
Trade Impact	Discourages imports, encourages local production	Limits competition via branding rather than price manipulation

Source: the author. alessandro@unb.br

Which is better for customer? It is a national trade and internal production policy. A tariff is a direct barrier that raises the cost of foreign goods. Tariffs manipulate market prices directly by making foreign goods more expensive. Protection like a mark restricts competition by legally defining product identity or origin, which can create a monopoly effect on specific brands or regional products. Thus, protections do not impose direct financial barriers but create a perceived quality distinction that influences consumer choice.

A trademarked or certified product signals authenticity, quality, and exclusivity. Consumers often associate these products with higher value and prestige, allowing producers to charge a premium. Protected marks create a unique market segment that competitors cannot legally imitate. Instead of competing purely on price, firms compete based on reputation, tradition, or region of origin.

Table 2 - Key Difference: Tariff vs. Mark-Based Protection

Feature	Tariffs	Marks (e.g., trademarks, GIs, certification marks)
Direct Price Impact	Increases import costs	Allows higher pricing via exclusivity
Effect on Domestic Competition	Reduces foreign competition by making imports costlier	Creates premium market segments, not cost barriers
Consumer Perception	Higher prices on foreign goods may discourage buying	Enhances perceived quality and desirability
Revenue Generation	Government collects tariff revenue	No government revenue, but firms benefit from branding

Source: the author. alessandro@unb.br

Towards origin of products, the U.S. and China have different interpretations and approaches to product origin protection, particularly in Geographical Indications (GIs) and local trademarks. Their legal frameworks reflect their economic and trade policies, leading to differences in intellectual property (IP) enforcement and market regulation (Aveni 2019).

U.S. approach favors trademarks over geographical indications and sees GIs as a subset of trademark law, rather than a separate system of protection. In the U.S., a GI is usually registered as a certification mark or collective mark under the Lanham Act 1946 (U.S. 1946). An example is "Idaho Potatoes" which is a certification mark, meaning only potatoes grown in Idaho can use the name⁸.

The focus is ensuring that trademarks and certification marks identify product quality without restricting use. Unlike the European model (where GIs are a public good controlled by producer groups), U.S. law allows private entities to own and enforce GI rights. The "Roquefort" cheese is a GI in Europe but a trademark in the U.S., owned by the French cheese producers.

The U.S. often refuses to recognize foreign GIs if they are considered generic terms in American commerce thus, the U.S. does not protect "Parmesan" as an exclusive GI, arguing that it is a generic term for a type of cheese, whereas, in Europe, only cheese from Parma, Italy can be called "Parmigiano Reggiano.". USA believes that overly strict GI protections restrict fair competition and consumer choice (Aveni 2019).

China takes a hybrid approach, recognizing GIs under both trademark law and special GI regulations, influenced by European and WTO standards. China adopted a

⁸ <https://www.uspto.gov/ip-policy/trademark-policy/geographical-indications>

Dual Protection System for GIs: Trademark-Based GI Protection (like the U.S.) and a Public GI System (similar to the European model regulated by the State Administration for Market Regulation (SAMR). China sometimes refuses foreign companies' attempts to register GIs as trademarks if they conflict with state-recognized GIs (Aveni 2019).

China has Strong Enforcement, Especially for Domestic GIs. The Chinese government actively enforces GIs, especially for domestically significant products like Pu'er Tea or Moutai Liquor. To make an exchange with Europe China has strengthened its GI protections, especially after signing the EU-China GI Agreement (EU 2021), which protects 100 European GIs in China and 100 Chinese GIs in Europe.

Table 3 - Key Differences Between the USA and China on Product Origin Protection

Feature	USA (Trademark-Based GI System)	China (Hybrid GI System)
Legal Framework	Lanham Act (Trademark Law)	Trademark Law + Public GI System
Main Protection Mechanism	Certification or Collective Marks	Certification Marks + National GI Recognition
View on Foreign GIs	Often rejected if seen as "generic"	Recognized if registered under bilateral agreements
Example of Dispute	"Parmesan" (U.S. considers it generic, EU disagrees)	"Pu'er Tea" (China enforces it as a state GI)
Government Role	Minimal (focus on free market)	Strong government enforcement
International Agreements	Weaker GI recognition in trade deals	Signed EU-China GI Agreement (2021)

Source: the author. alessandro@unb.br

As a result, the U.S. model treats GIs as a trademark, focusing on market competition. It prioritizes business flexibility and rejects the over-protection of product names. The Chinese model follows a mixed approach, using both trademark law and government GI recognition, increasingly aligning with European-style GI protections. That different interpretation provokes conflicts in international trade, particularly in food and beverage industries, where European producers demand stricter GI protections.

The U.S. argues for greater flexibility and the Chinese are not trustworthy in the protection of marks and GI is weaker.

On the other side, Europe's Interpretation of product origin protection (Geographical Indications – GIs). In Europe, product origin protection is highly developed and strongly regulated under a system that treats Geographical Indications (GIs) as public goods rather than private trademarks. The European Union (EU) sees GIs as a way to preserve cultural heritage, ensure quality, and provide economic benefits to local producers.

The European portion based on Terroir's interpretation states that GIs are separate from Trademarks. Unlike the United States, the EU considers GIs a distinct intellectual property right, linked to a specific geographic region and traditional production methods. In the EU, only products that meet strict regional production and quality standards can use a protected name.

The regulation in Europe in agriculture states GI organizations must explain the process of the products and the origin of the product. The same doesn't apply to other products. The origin declaration is a differentiation that is complementary to the mark and is a guarantee for the customer. Today we are buying products whose components are made worldwide and commercialized with marks. So in fact, we don't know the origin of the product we buy.

In conflict with the U.S. interpretation, GIs are public, not privately owned GIs belong to producer groups, not individual companies. Only registered producers in the region can use the GI name. Protection Extends Beyond the EU and the EU negotiates bilateral agreements to extend GI protections globally. There are the European Court Cases and Trade Disputes but the WTO ruled that countries are not required to protect GIs if a name has become generic in their market (favoring the U.S.). That is the GATT agreement while WIPO tried to negotiate a neutral position with the Geneva Act ⁹(Aveni 2019).

The GIs in Europe, under the terroir concept, are a cultural and economic asset, protecting regional traditions and small producers (Aveni 2024). The strict PDO and PGI system ensures that only quality products use GI names. The EU fights hard against "genericization", banning similar names and even suggestive terms (e.g., "Greek-style cheese" instead of "Feta"). As in Brazil, that position is considered valid in many countries (Faria and Aveni 2023).

Unlike the U.S. free-market approach, the EU actively defends its GIs worldwide in the name of terroir definition but each national legislation has different approaches and it is important to explain that problem with a summary case study. At the end of the study, it will be more clear the issues about protection and why and when to use distinction marks as an alternative strategy against tariffs.

⁹ <https://www.wipo.int/treaties/en/registration/lisbon/> and <https://www.wipo.int/wipolex/en/treaties/textdetails/15625>

Table 4 - GI vs TradeMark differentiations for some countries

Feature	European Union (EU)	United States (USA)	China
GI vs. Trademark	GIs are separate from trademarks	GIs are trademarks (certification marks)	Hybrid system (GIs + trademarks)
Who Owns a GI?	Producer groups, not private companies	Can be privately owned trademarks	Mix of public and private ownership
Generic Terms?	Strong protection, bans generic use	Allows generic use (e.g., "Parmesan")	Protects local GIs, but weaker for foreign GIs
Legal Enforcement	Strict EU regulation, can sue misuse cases	Limited enforcement, market-driven approach	Strong enforcement for domestic GIs, increasing protection for foreign ones
International Recognition	Expands GI protection via trade agreements	Limited GI recognition in trade deals	Signed EU-China GI Agreement

Source: the author. alessandro@unb.br

3.3. Tariffs 2025 struggle.

A tariff increase is not only a country unilateral action. There was a chain of international trading problems during the last decades. For example China started a tariff war on export tariffs on rare minerals needed for the third sector in the U.S.. The creation of the Euro was the European declaration of war against the dollar and the recent BIRCS declaration to create a currency alternative to the dollar (and Euro) is another problem not on tariffs but about the rate of exchange (Jackson 2006). Thus there are no good and bad guys in a trade war, and it is important to seek overall trends and the global context. Anyway a change in industry and service led to a different framework of the global economy and could also be a change driven by new protectionism.

U.S. Recent tariffs and importation limitation speech increase panic in the markets¹⁰. Panic or retaliation is not a correct answer and all negotiation must be started having in mind a strategy. On April 2, 2025, Trump's speech cited the National Trade Estimate Report (NTE) on Foreign Trade Barriers (USTR 2025), providing a comprehensive analysis of significant obstacles hindering U.S. exports, foreign direct investment, and electronic commerce across global markets. This annual report serves as a critical tool for identifying and addressing trade barriers that affect U.S. economic interests.

The purpose of the NTE Report is to identify issues the U.S. Government seeks to remove including non-market policies and practices. These are: 1) targeting industrial sectors for dominance, 2) non-market excess capacity, and 3) distorting activities of state-owned or state-sponsored firms. All these no-tariff practices create economic and national security risks and undermine U.S. competitiveness.

The NTE Report (USTR 2025) also underscores concerns related to sanitary and phytosanitary (SPS) measures, technical barriers to trade (TBT), and other non-tariff barriers that impede U.S. exports. For instance, the National Pork Producers Council (NPPC) has highlighted burdensome facility registration requirements and non-science-based import licensing that limit U.S. pork exports to various countries.

The Report (NTE 2025) affirmed¹¹: "Trade barriers ... may be broadly defined as government laws, regulations, policies, or practices, including non-market policies and practices, that distort or undermine fair competition.... These definitions include measures that protect domestic goods and services from foreign competition, artificially stimulate exports of particular domestic goods and services, or fail to provide adequate and effective protection of intellectual property rights".

Thus, President Trump's speech motivations for imposing new tariffs are driven by economic, political, and strategic motivations because tariffs are a tool to strengthen U.S. industries, reduce trade deficits, and exert leverage over global competitors. High tariffs could encourage companies to produce goods within the U.S. instead of outsourcing to countries like China and Mexico. By taxing imports the economic theory says it incentivizes domestic production, thus increasing employment in manufacturing sectors. National security for the U.S. imply to be self-sufficient or, at least sufficient, in many activities and sectors lost in the last decades and substituted by imports.

U.S. trade deficit (especially with China) has remained high thus, the tariff probability will be reduced by making American goods more competitive or increasing the internal U.S. market. Protectionist trade policies to revive U.S. manufacturing, particularly in industrial states like Pennsylvania, Ohio, and Michigan. Another strategic trade motivation is strengthening U.S. leverage in future trade negotiations using tariffs as bargaining chips. Tariffs pressure countries to negotiate better trade terms with the U.S. By disrupting the status quo, Trump may force partners into renegotiating trade agreements that favor the U.S.

Last but not least we must consider that the supply chain needs also strategic security concerns. President Trump believes that dependence on foreign goods, especially critical materials like semiconductors and rare earth metals, is a U.S. security risk. In that sense, tariffs on steel, aluminum, and technology products are justified as necessary for national security under the International Emergency Economic Powers Act (IEEPA).

¹⁰ <https://www.reuters.com/world/reaction-trumps-steep-tariffs-mexico-canada-china-2025-02-03/>

¹¹ The report highlight the context for all Nations trade with U.S. and the figures in Appendix II of the report explained with quantitative effect the U.S. Goods Trade for Select Trade Partners in Rank Order of U.S. Goods Exports, 2023-2024 (Values in Millions of Dollars).

Starting a tariff war, and trying to define new strategies, will risk retaliation and trade war escalation. Countries like China, the EU, and Mexico have threatened retaliatory tariffs, which could lead to higher prices for American consumers and economic instability. It is credible that higher import tariffs can drive up costs for businesses and consumers, leading to inflationary pressures. In another alternative customers could choose also not to buy costly imported goods.

Major U.S. companies that rely on global supply chains (like Apple, Tesla, and Ford) may suffer declining profits. Many U.S. industries depend on global suppliers, particularly in China, Vietnam, and Mexico. Tariffs make it more expensive and difficult to import parts. An option is to sell less or to build factories in the U.S. Small businesses often lack the resources to absorb higher import costs, making it harder for them to compete. Unlike large corporations, they cannot shift supply chains to avoid tariffs. In that sense, tariff war increases prices, worsening inflation, which all the Central Banks have been trying to control.

It is a fact that tariff increase policies undermine the credibility of trade deals like USMCA, WTO agreements, and the CPTPP. Countries may abandon trade negotiations and seek alternative alliances (e.g., China with Europe or Japan and Korea). However, that is not Trump's fault because the global agencies have not solved all issues of free world trade or negotiations needed. It seems all negotiations followed a bilateral scheme in the last decades.

The agencies and mechanisms to negotiate structural changes had failed as was evident before 2025, in the USA-China trade war in 2018. The rise of China and India (with the expanded BRICS group), and the changes in the European production sector tighter with the third sector development in the U.S., only suggest it is time to renegotiate new trade rules between nations. If Trump will be the catalyst of the new order or a simple temporal agent neither USA nor economy experts can predict before the new order and a new equilibrium will be reached.

4. Study Case: economic application in Brazil strategy.

In that section, we aim to explain how much a strategy based on M, CM, and GI is consistent and robust. We explore if it is possible to use that considering the bilateral agreements to bypass tariffs. We focus on Brazil's legislation and trade to understand how much it is worth and what is important for Brazilian trade.

In Brazil, trademarks, collective marks, and geographical indications are regulated by Law No. 9.279/1996 (BRAZIL 1996), which governs the rights and protection of industrial property, including patents, trademarks, and geographical indications. A trademark (*marca*) is a distinctive sign used to identify and differentiate goods or services from others in the market. Brazilian law recognizes different trademarks, including word marks, figurative marks, composite marks, and three-dimensional marks. (Aveni, 2019, 2024)

Law 9.279 / 1996 Article 122: Defines trademarks as visually perceptible distinctive signs that can be used to distinguish products and services. Article 123: Classifies trademarks into three categories: Product or service marks (to distinguish products or services), Certification marks (to attest conformity to technical norms), and Collective marks (used by associations or groups). Article 129 establishes that trademark ownership is acquired through registration at the INPI.

A collective mark (*marca coletiva*) is a trademark used by a group, association, or cooperative to distinguish their goods or services. A collective mark does not belong to a single company but to a collective entity that sets rules for its use. Article 123(III): Defines a collective mark as a sign identifying products or services from members of

an entity. Article 128, Paragraph 1: Only legal entities representing a collective interest can apply for a collective mark. Article 147: Requires the entity to submit a regulation of use, establishing the conditions for using the collective mark.

Geographical Indications (GIs) in Brazil (*indicação geográfica*, IG) refers to a specific region or locality known for producing a distinctive product due to its unique environmental factors or traditional know-how. Types of Geographical Indications (Law 9.279/1996 Article 177): *Indicação de Procedência* (IP) – Indication of Origin that Granted when a region is well known for producing a product. *Denominação de Origem* (DO) – Designation of Origin requires proof that the region's climate, soil, or other natural factors affect the product's characteristics. Article 178 adds that only entities representing local producers or service providers can request recognition. GIs are registered at INPI and can be used exclusively by producers from the designated region and State of the Federation.

Table 5 - Key Differences Between Trademarks, Collective Marks, and Geographical Indications

Feature	Trademark (Marca)	Collective Mark (Marca Coletiva)	Geographical Indication (IG)
Ownership	Individual/company	Association or cooperative	Producers from a specific region
Purpose	Identifies a single brand	Identifies members of a group	Identifies regional products
Registration	INPI	INPI	INPI
Duration	10 years, renewable	10 years, renewable	No expiration (if region maintains reputation)
Example	"Havaianas" (flip-flops)	"SIC" (cooperative mark)	"Parmesão de Pernambuco" (cheese)

Source: the author. alessandro@unb.br

All three are regulated by Brazil's Industrial Property Law (Law No. 9.279/1996) and administered by INPI. The only protection for local production and customers is GI, thus the regulation goal for each is the following:

- Trademarks protect brand identity for businesses.
- Collective marks allow groups to share a common brand identity.

- Geographical Indications protect the reputation of regional products.

There are at the end of 2024, 125 recognized geographical indications, but Brazil has great potential to expand them. The academy and agencies like SEBRAE are not fully involved in increasing Geographical Indications GI continues to remain lower than the potential and the number is dramatically low compared to Europe (more than 2 thousand GIs).

The tariff's motivation to increase GI academic analyses are much more interested in legal aspects than marketing and trade and theoretical assumptions (AVENI and FARIA 2024). The recent agreement with Europe clarifies that the Brazilian government is not very much interested in GI and more interested in marks following China and USA interpretations. Thus, the GI agreement in the European-Mercosur is only an appendix of the main contract (Aveni 2019).

We see in the analysis above that, against globalization, the agricultural sector needs protection and special consideration about tariffs. It must consider the concept of the ability (tradition) of a particular country to produce all the food necessary to feed its population with a focus on food products: rice, corn, and tubers citrate. Thus a possible strategy for Brazil and Europe, considering the low tariff between Brazil and the U.S., against the higher tariff between Europe and the U.S. helps possible interesting solutions of new flows (i.e. from Europe to Brazil and then to the U.S. as a mark) and new markets (expand Brazil - Europe GI import-export).

Brazilian and European legislation, out of the practice, has similarities and an agreement on agricultural products could be useful for both. Mercosur, which has fewer tariffs than Europe, could export from Europe to the U.S. or be a road to join the U.S. market with the lowest tariffs only with different trademarks.

Increasing bilateral trade between Mercosul and Europe, out of BRICS, is a strategy that strengthens independence from main actors like the U.S. and China and raises the price for these countries to negotiate international trade with a less dominant position. In other words, if Brazil and Europe they will have more negotiation power to resist pressure from the world-dominating countries because both will need to have the Brazil-European block on their side. The increase in trade between Europe and Mercosur with a low tariff level will compensate for the decrease in sales in the U.S.

Only GI protects local agriculture and is an alternative reaction to tariffs while marks and collective marks have different functions. Brazil's protection will help to expand European exports in the region and that could be a strong point for negotiations of other products and services. If U.S. tariffs continue to rise, an agreement with Europe and increase of trade can substitute volume losses. Thus a bilateral strategy to create an alternative market Europe - Mercosur with low internal tariffs. That will compensate for losses and increase volumes for both.

Finally it must be added that in the European Union, the application of customs duties on goods coming from third countries (i.e., non-member states) is governed by a common set of rules as part of the EU's common commercial policy. This means that individual Member States cannot impose duties on their own and all measures must be decided at the EU level. The same for Mercosur that is governed primarily by the Treaty of Asunción (1991) and later protocols Internal trade (between members). For disputes or responses to unfair trade within Mercosur, individual states cannot request consultations or initiate dispute for general external tariffs under the *Ouro Preto* Protocol and Common External Tariff CET rules. An agreement between many countries is difficult but was successfully started.

5. Discussion Results

Towards trade strategies towards tariffs and barriers, Mark and Collective Marks are weak and less valuable variables to use as a strategic choice against tariff increases. A luxury item could have some chance to continue to sell because of customer health. The tariffs don't reduce the number of customers. The problem with luxury goods is that they are few and their customers, even with high purchase power are only niches.

Anyone could understand the impact of a fixed tariff is more affordable for people with high rents and that could compensate the cost of life with a new millionaire contract with some brand or movie producer, than the average worker with a salary that could rise usually less than the tariff increase. The taxation rates must be progressive and generally tariffs are fixed to have an impact on the mass market. A government increase in revenue from luxury trade is not an option also because the level of labor and the number of consumers, that are the voting major group means a differentiated welfare, actually not negotiable.

Thus, the local product protection of a GI, as the terroir tradition in Europe, could be a real protection for producers in the internal market and export. The agricultural origin and the principle of food security and sovereignty, emphasize local food economies, and sustainable food availability, and center culturally appropriate foods and practices. GI is also important for food self-sufficiency. That's one reason why Europe has barriers to import food and defend local production.

According to Prajal Pradhan and Ali (2014), a region is self-sufficient¹² in food when its total calorie production is enough to meet its demand. Globally, about 1.9 billion people are self-sufficient while about 1 billion people from Asia and Africa required cross-continental agricultural trade in 2000. The number of people depending on international trade will vary between 1.5 and 6 billion by 2050. Climate change may increase the need for agricultural trade by 4% to 16%.

According to Kaufmann and Ali (2022), 14 % of EU regions were self-sufficient, 26 % were import-dependent for all three dimensions, 54 % of regions were self-sufficient for ruminant livestock products and 39 % for monogastric livestock products underlining a spatially concentrated pork, egg, and poultry production structure in the EU. Moreover, 21 % of regions depend on crop imports and are simultaneously self-sufficient or net exporters of livestock products.

The food self-sufficient in European countries¹³, as France's food sovereignty declines, the agricultural power of countries like Poland and Spain, must face the cost of intensifying farming practices that harm the environment. European dairy production currently seems more than sufficient to meet demand, but the downsizing of the dairy herd to meet environmental goals could eventually halt these dynamics also because of risks like disease reductions recently impacting American egg production¹⁴ (Prajal, et al 2014, Stein and Santini. 2022, Kaufmann et al, 2022)

We need to understand that, for agriculture, an environmental constraint, means to depend on the production of nations with less constraint like the replacement of the industry production. European production, pursuing the goal of reducing greenhouse gas emissions or reducing the use of pesticides or OGM, accompanied by rising production costs, must be supported and protected. The increase in more competitive agricultural imports, could be worse than carbon and environmental footprint and

¹² <https://doi.org/10.4060/cd2971en>

¹³ <https://www.agriculture-strategies.eu/en/2024/10/european-food-sovereignty-what-do-the-numbers-say/>

¹⁴ <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2025/mar/04/egg-prices-bird-flu-corporate-profits>

reduce self-sufficiency. Again a GI process complies with environmental protection and is better than industrial products.

From the discussion above we guess to summarize some key facts:

1) Tariffs impacts. They are elements in strategy and strategic negotiation between economies. Less or more tariffs and bilateral agreements are a continuous process that includes changes caused by internal and international changes in trade. In the last decades, the U.S. and Europe lost their industrial power and decentralized production. China gained space and volumes opening the internal market that reached more than a billion potential customers. National diversified activity sectors, services (mainly information technologies), and supply chains are the new frontiers where tariffs will be tested to confirm their full validity in the future. The actual tariff struggle will help to develop new complex emerging strategies and use of barriers or product marks.

2) Marks, Collective Marks, and GI as trade barriers strategies.

Mark and collective marks could be more impacted by tariffs not because the customers will consume their favorite brand but because of the reduction of the spendable amount of money. Usually, tariffs do not follow the increasing rate of salary growth. The unique protection is quality and regional trade. We could claim GI impacts on customers (the traditions) or the logistic cost that relatively reduces the will to seek similar products far from home, but whatever we claim the customer preference is probably, especially for agricultural products and wines, a local-driven choice. Trade barriers cannot be changed easily by a policy or a direct tariff. Even in a world of free trade intellectual property will create issues with a free flow of products.

3) International strategy for trade and tariff.

To respond to an aggressive alternative, whatever reasons, good or bad support it, every country has different possible options: reduce export to the U.S., sell in other markets, lower prices, decentralize to the U.S. some production, and so on. The Brazil case of applied economy shows that European Countries are in the worst position because the European Union has a higher level of constraint than Brazil. In any case, all national policies must be negotiated under a web of treaties and regulations. Economic globalization implies that every tariff shock from whatever country impacts other economies more than before, and globalization implies a tight International trade network that is difficult to separate for Regions and Nations. The more independence of global trade growth the fewer tariffs could help develop world trade. Developed world trade must be fair.

Global market has less impact on Geographical Indications in the local or regional market and customers' preferences for quality and traditional products than marks. Marks and collective marks are not protections or instruments for valorization and territory protection as the GI with the terroir interpretation. The European terroir paradigm helps GI to maintain levels of trade and market and it is a protection because of its intimate relation with the territory: producers and customers. We must also consider that practices in all countries are different from legal definitions (Aveni 2019).

Thus, the terroir paradigm and the consequent GI local protection have legal and international protection and are a trade barrier, not a tariff. We guess GI is the only trade protection because of legislation and the tight relationship with customers that could bypass the national taxation of imported products. GI defends local production,

quality, and self-sufficiency and is relatively less impacted by import tariffs when the product is exported. Examples are GI wine or alcoholics.

Europe on 20 July 2020 agreed with Pequim to protect 100 EU GIs in China and 100 Chinese GIs in the EU against imitation and usurpation like the European-Mercosul Agreement. To bypass tariffs it is good for Brazil and Europe develop the European-Mercosur Agreement of 2019¹⁵. That could be mutual protection from the U.S. or China international trade decisions and tariffs increase. The total market of Europe and Mercosur, with the trade developing opportunities in Mercosur, is good protection against tariffs attack better than bilateral agreement of two nations as the actual short term policy

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The international tariffs framework is complex. Tariffs are different for every sector of activities in which the primary sector in history had protection and continuous to have it. The discussion research paper starts with basic international trade tariff rules and intellectual property. There is no way for global free traffic in agricultural markets and trade. It is also difficult to believe trade without barriers protecting local markets. The research discusses marks, trademarks, and geographical indications as an alternative way to protect the market without tariffs. That is the main reason for structural international agricultural market differentiation.

An explanation of the actual context of tariff turbulence to explore the meaning of tariffs and their function in the international and internal markets followed the first section. Motivations for protection are many and include security and national ones. Finally, the discussion was on the Brazilian case, because of the previous research of the author in intellectual property economics, and the legislation that allows GI as a pivot to react to international tariff pressures. In the Brazilian case, we found weak interest in expanding GI as an internal asset and using it as a trade strategy. We suggested instead using the European-Mercosur agreement both to bypass the new tariff dilemma and to develop new markets.

As a result, we guess the European terroir-driven interpretation of GI allows it to be a strong strategy defense and option against tariff increases. Mark or collective marks do not have strong roots in local production, processes, and customers, so they are subjected to a tariff war. Moreover, customers will continue to purchase GI products even with higher prices due to tax. A contraction could be a substitute opening new markets where a new middle class can afford high-quality products prices.

We believe tariffs and economic theory and their impacts are not rights or false as M. Blaug (1997) always suggested. Not all goods, and services (no GI services signs in Europe) could be protected with a GI. All goods with marks will suffer a market contraction due to higher prices but with individual differences. Cross-protection and tariff reduction could be negotiated within GI bilateral agreements like Europe-China and Europe-Mercosul. However, even if GI interpretations are different nothing impedes a cross-agreement with U.S. marks and GI. A possible export strategy is the local trade protection on GI in agriculture based on quality and local signs inside of brands avoiding the increase of tariff impacts.

There is no necessity to expand GI protection to products and services like suggested in some countries like Brazil. It seems more interesting to create new types of barriers using the idea of cultural heritage or cultural/historical district. That is an idea from Italy. These products and services will have some export difficulty but have

¹⁵ https://policy.trade.ec.europa.eu/eu-trade-relationships-country-and-region/countries-and-regions/mercosur/eu-mercosur-agreement_en

a local preference or a complementary touristic package. Agricultural GI is, definitely, an alternative strategy of a tariff war.

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